

New Synthesis of Alnustone, Tagetone and Dihydrotagetone from β -Ketophosphonate

O. P. VIG*, S. S. BARI, M. A. SATTAR, SANJIV SHARMA and NALINI MAHAJAN

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 5 July 1988, revised 4 November 1988, accepted 18 November 1988

Alnustone (1) has been synthesised through the Emmons-Horner modified Wittig reaction using β -ketophosphonate (6) and cinnamaldehyde. Tagetone (7) and dihydrotagetone (8) have been synthesised using common β -ketophosphonate (10) on reaction with vinyl methyl ketone and acetaldehyde respectively.

β -Ketophosphonates are important reagents of olefination at a desired position with specific stereochemistry through Emmons-Horner modification of the Wittig reaction¹⁻³. In this paper we report the very short route syntheses of three naturally occurring compounds alnustone (1), tagetone (7) and dihydrotagetone (8) by making use of β -ketophosphonate.

Alnustone, 1,7-diphenyl-1(*E*),3(*E*)-heptadien-5-one (1) was isolated from *Alnus pendula* matsum⁴. The structure (1) was further confirmed by syntheses^{5,6}. Benzyl alcohol (2) on treatment with mesyl chloride⁷ gave benzylmethane sulphonate (3), and the crude mesylate (3) was reacted with sodium salt of malonic ester in anhydrous benzene/DMF⁸ to secure the diester (4). The diester thus obtained was decarboxylated⁹ by heating the compound with moist NaCl in DMSO leading to the formation of the monoester (5). Acylation of lithium dimethylmethyl phosphonate using the ester (5) at -78° under N_2 atmosphere in dry THF gave the desired β -ketophosphonate (6) which was reacted with cinnamaldehyde through the Wittig Emmons-Horner's reaction to furnish alnustone (1). The spectral data of the purified product (1) was similar to that reported in the literature⁴⁻⁶ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The acyclic monoterpenic ketones tagetone (7)¹¹⁻¹³ and dihydratagetone (8)¹⁴ were isolated

from *Tagetes glandulifera* by Jones and Smith¹⁰. The present studies incorporate¹⁵⁻¹⁷ the syntheses of tagetone and dihydrotagetone from the same β -ketophosphonate (10). The β -ketophosphonate, dimethyl-2-oxo-4-methylpentylphosphonate (10) was obtained through the direct acylation of lithium dimethylmethyl phosphonate by ethyl 3-methylbutanoate (9) in quantitative yields. Modified Wittig reaction of the β -ketophosphonate (10) with methylvinyl ketone and acetaldehyde in dry DME using NaH as base gave tagetone (7) and 2-methylhept-2(*E*)-en-one (11) respectively. The compound 11 has already been converted to dihydrotagetone¹⁴ through 1,4-addition of the Grignard reagent vinylmagnesium bromide in the presence of cuprous iodide. This work constitutes the total synthesis of dihydrotagetone (8) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

Microanalyses were carried out in the Micro-analytical Section of R.S.I.C., Panjab University, Chandigarh. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrometer using thin liquid film, ¹H nmr spectra (CCl₄ or CDCl₃) at 90 MHz on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer, uv spectra was

recorded on a Hitachi 380 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a VG micromass 7070 F spectrometer. Silica gel 100–200 mesh (Acme) was used for column chromatography. Tlc performed on silica gel G. Unless otherwise stated all the organic extracts were dried over sodium sulphate.

Benzyl-methane-sulphonate (3): Mesyl chloride (15 g, 130.9 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) was added to a stirred solution of the alcohol (2; 10.8 g, 100 mmol) and Et_3N (15.0 g, 179 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) at 0 to -10° . The mixture was stirred for 1 h and worked up to give mesylate (15.44 g, 83%).

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-3-phenylpropionate (4): The crude mesylate (12.4 g, 66.67 mol) from the previous step was added to the ethyl sodiomalonate prepared from sodium (1.67 g, 73.33 mmol) and ethyl malonate (11.0 g, 68.73 mmol) in dry benzene in presence of DME (10 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 16 h. It was then washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent and chromatography over SiO_2 using petroleum ether–ether (5 : 1) furnished the diester (4; 10.5 g, 63%) (Found: C, 67.30; H, 7.0. Requires: C, 67.2; H, 7.2%); ν_{max} (neat) 2950, 1735 (C=O), 1590, 1450, 1380 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.20 (6H, t), 3.15 (2H, d), 3.5 (1H, t), 4.1 (4H, q), 7.3 (5H, s, ArH).

Ethyl 3-phenylpropionate (5): The diester (4; 5 g, 20.0 mmol) was heated for 9 h at $160-65^\circ$ in DMSO (50 ml) containing a few drops of water (0.72 g, 40 mmol) and sodium chloride (1.30 g, 22.2 mmol). The usual work-up and subsequent chromatography over SiO_2 using petroleum ether–ether (4 : 1) furnished the ester (5; 3.1 g, 87%) (Found: C, 74.32; H, 7.91. Requires: C, 74.15; H, 7.87%); ν_{max} (neat) 2930, 1750 (C=O), 1595, 1480 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.20 (3H, t), 2.6 (2H, t), 2.90 (2H, t), 4.10 (2H, q) and 7.30 (5H, s, ArH).

Dimethyl 2-oxo-4-phenylbutylphosphonate (6): A hexane solution of *n*-butyl lithium (6 ml, 10 mmol; 1.6 M) was added to a solution of dimethyl methylphosphonate (1.24 g, 10 mmol) in dry THF (15 ml) under N_2 at -78° for 5 min keeping temperature below -80° . Then the ester (0.9 g, 5.03 mmol) in dry THF (15 ml) was added to the reaction mixture at such a rate that temperature never exceeded -70° . The mixture was stirred for 30 min at low temperature and 30 min at room temperature. Then water (5 ml) was added and the reaction mixture stirred for further 1 h. It was then poured into ether (75 ml) and the organic layer extracted with 5% NH_4Cl (2×15 ml) and brine (2×15 ml). The aqueous layer was acidified to pH 3 with concentrated HCl and extracted with ether (2×25 ml). The ether solution was back-extracted with water (20 ml, pH 3) and the combined organic layer was dried, and evaporation of solvent and chromatography of the residue on SiO_2 using petroleum ether–ether (3 : 1) gave the phosphonate (6, yellow oil; 1.15 g, 89%) (Found: C, 56.12; H, 6.2. Requires: C, 56.8; H, 6.6%); ν_{max} (neat) 2900,

1690, 1700, 1250, 1030, 800 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 2.80 (4H, m, Ph- CH_2CO), 2.94 (2H, d, J 21Hz, $\text{COCH}_2-\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2)_2$), 3.75 (6H, d, J 7Hz, $\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2)_2$) and 7.30 (5H, s, ArH).

1,7-Diphenyl-1(E),3(E)-heptadien-5-one (1): A solution of the oxophosphonate (6; 850 mg, 3.32 mmol) in DME (3 ml) was added dropwise to NaH (185 mg, 4.02 mmol). The resulting clear solution was stirred for 20 h at room temperature and the usual work-up and chromatography over neutral alumina gave 1, which was recrystallised from benzene–petroleum ether (620 mg, 62%), m.p. $60.5-61^\circ$ (Found: C, 86.70; H, 6.96. Requires: C, 86.98; H, 6.91%); λ_{max} 327 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.4, CH_2OH); ν_{max} (nujol) 1665 (CO), 1600, 990, 750 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 2.9 (4H, m, Ph- $(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CO}$), 6.3 (1H, d, J 15Hz, $\text{COCH}=\text{}$), 6.9 (2H, m, $=\text{CHCH}=\text{}$), 7.3 (5H, s, ArH) and 7.6 (6H, m, 5H, ArH and 1H olefinic proton).

Dimethyl 2-oxo-4-methyl-pentylphosphonate (10): To a solution of dimethylmethylphosphonate (12.4 g, 100 mmol) in dry THF (150 ml) under N_2 at 78° was added dropwise *n*-butyllithium (45.5 ml, 100.10 mmol, 2.2 M in hexane). Ethyl isovalerate (6.5 g, 50 mmol) was then added to it and worked up according to the procedure described for 6. Evaporation of the solvent followed by chromatographic purification of the residue on silica gel eluting with petroleum ether–ethyl acetate (2 : 1) furnished the phosphonate (10.10 g, 97%) (Found: C, 46.04; H, 8.00. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{P}$ requires: C, 46.15; H, 8.17%); ν_{max} (neat) 2900, 1600, 1350, 1260 and 1050 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.95 (6H, d, J 7Hz, CH_3CHCH_2), 1.30 (1H, m, CH_2CHCH_2), 2.50 (2H, d, CH_2CH), 3.06 (2H, d, J 23Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2)_2$) and 3.95 (6H, d, J 11Hz, $-\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2)_2$).

2,6-Dimethyl-5,7-octadien-4-one (tagetone, 7): To a slurry of 50% NaH (0.53 g, 11.04 mmol) washed with *n*-hexane placed in DME (10 ml) was added the phosphonate (10; 2.3 g, 11.06 mmol) dropwise at room temperature. To the resulting clear solution was added methyl vinyl ketone (0.70 g, 10.0 mmol) slowly at $0-5^\circ$ and stirring was continued for 4–5 h at 20° . The reaction mixture was worked up according to the procedure reported for 1. Evaporation of the solvent and column chromatography over neutral alumina afforded 7 (0.85 g, 51%) (Found: C, 54.60; H, 8.50. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires: C, 55.17; H, 8.05%); λ_{max} (CH_2OH) 265 nm (ϵ 18 000); ν_{max} (neat) 2980, 1680, 1630, 1365, 990, 915 and 325 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.93 (6H, d, J 6Hz, CH_3CHCH_2), 1.25 (1H, m, CH_2CHCH_2), 2.10 (3H, s, allylic CH_2), 2.25 (2H, d, COCH_2-), 4.15 (2H, d, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 6.30 (7H, s, $\text{COCH}=\text{}$) and 7.20 (1H, t, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$); *m/e* 152.

2-Methylhept-5(E)-en-4-one (11): The oxophosphonate (10; 2.0 g, 9.62 mmol) was treated with 50% NaH (0.525 g, 10.94 mmol) in DME slowly according to the procedure reported for 7. To the resulting clear solution was added acetaldehyde (0.48 g, 10.91 mmol) in DME at low temperature and the contents stirred for 1 h. The solvent was

evaporated and the residue after chromatographic purification over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent gave the enone (11; 1.0 g, 85%) (Found : C, 75.66; H, 10.80. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires : C, 76.19; H, 11.11%); λ_{max} (CH_2CH) 227 nm; ν_{max} (neat) 2980, 2960, 2880, 1680, 1640, 1370, 1450, 1370, 1300, 1200, 970, 790 and 765 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.95 (6H, d, J 6Hz, CH_2CHCH_2), 1.25 (1H, m, CH_2CHCH_2), 1.95 (3H, dd, J 9Hz and 2Hz, allylic CH_2), 2.35 (2H, d, J 6Hz, CH_2CO), 6.20 (1H, d, J 16Hz, $COCH=$) and 6.80-7.10 (H, m, $COCH=CHCH_2$); m/e 126.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Government of India for awarding scholarship to one of them (M.A.S.).

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